

Extraction of Vocal Features as Biomarkers for Heart Failure Diagnosis

Tijana Geroski, Lazar Dašić, Ognjen Pavić, Nenad Filipović Member, IEEE

Abstract— This paper explores the emerging role of vocal biomarkers in the diagnosis and management of heart failure. By analyzing voice characteristics, non-invasive methods offer new potential for early detection, patient self-management, and reducing healthcare costs associated with heart failure.

Clinical Relevance— Non-invasive vocal biomarkers could provide a valuable tool for timely monitoring disease detection, progression and guide treatment adjustments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heart Failure (HF), also referred to as congestive heart failure, is characterized by the heart's inability to pump sufficient blood to meet the body's metabolic needs [1]. Traditional methods for detecting HF primarily rely on clinical assessments, imaging techniques, and laboratory tests. Clinicians typically evaluate symptoms such as shortness of breath, fatigue, and fluid retention, alongside physical examination findings like jugular venous distention and peripheral edema [2]. While these traditional markers are widely used, the advent of biomarkers has significantly improved the early detection and management of HF [2]. Recently, attention has turned to non-invasive vocal biomarkers, which are transforming heart failure detection.

II. METHODS

The link between voice and heart failure originates from how the condition impacts the respiratory and cardiovascular systems, which can subsequently alter vocal characteristics. A key physiological basis for the connection between voice and heart failure is fluid retention and pulmonary congestion, which contribute to heart failure decompensation [3]. The methodology included extraction of identified features from the recorded voice signal. Five different recording tasks were formulated:

1. Reading the text out loud in the normal speaking tempo;
2. Free speech: talking for at least 30s about yesterday;
3. Number counting up - from 1 to 30;
4. Number counting down – from 30 to 1;
5. Maximum phonation test: saying “aaa” for as long as possible.

The audio signal is resampled to a target sampling rate of 16000 Hz using `librosa.resample`. The Mel spectrogram is

generated using `librosa.feature.melspectrogram`. The spectrogram is downsampled by averaging each 100x100 block to reduce its size. This is done to make the spectrogram more manageable while retaining significant features.

III. RESULTS

The CSV with extracted features were created as the output of voice analysis. A list of features was as following: total duration, total phonation time, total time from first to last phonation, number of pauses longer than 100ms, number of pauses longer than 500ms, longest pause (sec), standard deviation of pause lengths, longest continuous phonation, second longest continuous phonation, third longest continuous phonation, standard deviation of phonation lengths, number of phonation segments, mean pitch, standard deviation of pitch, mean loudness, standard deviation of loudness, mean mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCS), standard deviation of MFCCS, mean cepstral peak prominence (CPP), standard deviation of CPP, mean fundamental frequency (Hz), standard deviation of fundamental frequency, jitter, shimmer text.

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

New technologies and user-friendly tools are enabling HF patients to manage their condition more effectively through voice analysis, potentially lowering healthcare costs and improving self-care [4].

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Tijana Geroski and Nenad Filipović are with Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac and Bioengineering Research and Development Center (BioIRC) Kragujevac, Serbia (e-mail: tijanas@kg.ac.rs; fica@kg.ac.rs)

Lazar Dašić and Ognjen Pavić are with Institute of Information Technologies Kragujevac, Serbia and Bioengineering Research and Development Center (BioIRC) Kragujevac, Serbia (e-mail: lazar.dasic@kg.ac.rs; opavic@kg.ac.rs)